

The Intercultural Sensitivity in Education: Critical Thinking, Use of Technology and Cyberbullying

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Abstract

Introduction. In a globalized world, it becomes increasingly relevant to study people's levels of intercultural sensitivity, understood as the ability to know, appreciate and interact effectively with people from different cultures, particularly in cosmopolitan cities like Madrid. The study had three aims: first, to analyze the relationships between the different levels of intercultural sensitivity with socio-demographic variables, such as age, educational level and gender. Secondly, it is proposed to study the relationships between intercultural sensitivity, critical thinking and the use of technology in education. Finally, we analyze whether levels of intercultural sensitivity affect cyberbullying.

Method. We worked with a non-probabilistic sample of 835 participants who live in the city of Madrid, aged between 18 and 65 years old ($M = 40.85$; $SD = 14.01$) and 55.2% of the participants identified as woman.

Results. The main results indicated that there are differences between the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity, the educational level of the participants, gender and age. The higher the educational level, the greater intercultural sensitivity, also women presented higher levels compared to men and at a younger age, lower levels of intercultural sensitivity. Likewise, the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity were significantly and positively related to the levels of critical thinking of the participants and the use of technology in the educational field, that is, the greater the critical thinking and agreement with the use of technology, the greater the levels of intercultural sensitivity. Finally, significant differences were observed with respect to cyberbullying. That is, people who did not experience cyberbullying have higher levels of intercultural sensitivity compared to those who did.

Discussion and Conclusion. This study provides crucial initial insights for future research, demonstrating that enhanced intercultural sensitivity is linked to higher education, female gender, and younger age, and positively correlates with critical thinking and technology use in education. Notably, it also suggests a significant relationship between high intercultural sensitivity and reduced cyberbullying. The scope and limitations of the study are discussed, as well as the relationships with other psychosocial variables.

Keywords: Intercultural Sensitivity; Educational level; Critical Thinking; Use of Technology in Education; Cyberbullying.

Resumen

Introducción. En un mundo globalizado, se vuelve cada vez más relevante estudiar los niveles de sensibilidad intercultural de las personas, comprendida como la capacidad para conocer, apreciar e interactuar eficazmente con personas de diferentes culturas, particularmente en ciudades cosmopolitas como Madrid. El estudio tuvo tres objetivos: primero, analizar las relaciones entre los diferentes niveles de sensibilidad a la interculturalidad con variables sociodemográficas, como la edad, el nivel educativo y el género. En segundo lugar, se propone estudiar las relaciones entre la sensibilidad intercultural, el pensamiento crítico y el uso de la tecnología en la educación. Finalmente, analizamos si los niveles de sensibilidad intercultural afectan al ciberbullying.

Método. Se trabajó con una muestra no probabilística de 835 participantes residentes en la ciudad de Madrid, con edades entre 18 y 65 años ($M = 40,85$; $DT = 14,01$) y el 55,2% de los participantes se identificaron como mujeres.

Resultados. Los principales resultados indicaron que existen diferencias entre las dimensiones de sensibilidad intercultural, el nivel educativo de los participantes, género y edad. A mayor nivel educativo mayor sensibilidad intercultural, además las mujeres presentaron mayores niveles respecto a los hombres y a menor edad menores niveles de sensibilidad intercultural. Asimismo, las dimensiones de sensibilidad intercultural se relacionaron significativa y positivamente con los niveles de pensamiento crítico de los participantes y el uso de la tecnología en el ámbito educativo, es decir, a mayor pensamiento crítico y acuerdo con el uso de la tecnología, mayor mayores son los niveles de sensibilidad intercultural. Finalmente, se observaron diferencias significativas respecto al ciberbullying. Es decir, las personas que no sufrieron ciberbullying tienen mayores niveles de sensibilidad intercultural en comparación con quienes sí lo sufrieron.

Discusión y Conclusion: Este estudio proporciona ideas iniciales cruciales para futuras investigaciones, demostrando que una mayor sensibilidad intercultural está vinculada a la educación superior, el género femenino y la edad más joven, y se correlaciona positivamente con el pensamiento crítico y el uso de la tecnología en la educación. En particular, también sugiere una relación significativa entre una alta sensibilidad intercultural y una reducción del ciberacoso. Se discuten los alcances y limitaciones del estudio, así como las relaciones con otras variables psicosociales.

Palabras clave: Sensibilidad Intercultural; Nivel educacional; Pensamiento crítico; Uso de la Tecnología en la Educación; Ciberacoso.

Introduction

In today's world, the phenomena of globalization and connection are part of a social evolution that is reflected in the growing flow of people, ideas and cultures around the world (Castles et al., 2014). In Europe, and particularly in Spain, this phenomenon has become evident in recent years, according to the latest reports from the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2022), highlighting the need for greater competence in intercultural sensitivity (Bennet, 2013; Chen, 2014; Deardorff, 2012). That is, as Chen and Starosta (2000) define it, a greater capacity to be aware of, understand, appreciate, and interact effectively with people from different cultures, maintaining a positive attitude and respect for differences. Madrid, as the capital of Spain, stands out for its cultural diversity.

According to the National Institute of Statistics, Madrid is the region with the highest percentage of foreign population in Spain, a city that welcomes individuals of more than 170 different nationalities (INE, 2022). Because of the demographic changes that are occurring, intercultural education must be a priority on the Spanish political and educational agenda, with the aim of promoting social cohesion and coexistence between different cultural groups (Aguado et al., 2003). In this framework, educational institutions must become a primary setting in which to enhance intercultural sensitivity. In this regard, numerous studies (Ayala-Asencio, 2020; Etchezahar et al., 2023; Tirnaz & Haddad Narafshan, 2018) suggest that education plays an important role in the development of intercultural sensitivity.

Education plays a pivotal role in broadening individuals' horizons by exposing them to a myriad of cultures, thereby fostering respect and appreciation for both cultural differences and similarities. According to Sobkowiak (2016), educational experiences are instrumental in cultivating intercultural competence, which includes understanding, respecting, and valuing diverse cultural practices and viewpoints. This process begins with integrating multicultural content into the curriculum, encouraging students to engage with and reflect on diverse cultural narratives. Such engagement helps dismantle stereotypes and prejudices, promoting a more inclusive worldview. Moreover, education equips individuals with critical skills necessary for effective and appropriate interaction with people from different cultural backgrounds. Banks (2004) and Gay (2002) highlight that these skills are not merely about acquiring factual knowledge about other cultures but also involve developing empathy, open-mindedness, and adaptability. Empathy allows individuals to put themselves in others' shoes, fostering deeper

connections and understanding. Open-mindedness encourages the acceptance of different cultural norms and practices without immediate judgment. Adaptability, on the other hand, ensures that individuals can navigate and respond appropriately to various cultural contexts.

In the classroom, these skills are nurtured through diverse pedagogical strategies, such as collaborative projects, intercultural exchanges, and inclusive teaching practices. For instance, collaborative projects that involve students from different cultural backgrounds can provide practical opportunities for students to practice intercultural communication and cooperation. Intercultural exchanges, such as study abroad programs or virtual exchange programs, immerse students in different cultural environments, challenging them to apply their intercultural skills in real-world settings (Banks, 2004). Additionally, inclusive teaching practices that recognize and value the cultural diversity of students create a supportive learning environment where all students feel respected and valued. Teachers play a crucial role in modeling intercultural competence by demonstrating respect for cultural diversity and employing teaching methods that are responsive to the cultural backgrounds of their students (Etchezahar et al., 2023).

Therefore, the educational level, understood as the degree of academic training of individuals, could influence how they perceive and interact with other cultures (Banks, 2004; Chen & Starosta, 2000). Although education in general tends to promote openness to diversity (Moradi & Ghabanchi, 2019), there is a gap in the understanding of how different levels of academic training can be related to intercultural sensitivity (Gómez Yepes et al., 2023). Likewise, some previous studies have shown that factors such as age and educational level can influence the ability to interact and understand individuals from different cultures (Perry & Southwell, 2011). In turn, other findings suggest that gender may play a relevant role in the development of intercultural sensitivity, with women showing a greater disposition towards intercultural empathy (Fritz et al., 2001). According to the background, the levels of interculturality and demographic variables such as educational level, age and gender are significantly related (Wu, 2015).

In our increasingly globalized and interconnected world, intercultural sensitivity has become a crucial competence in education (Deardorff, 2012). Consequently, intercultural sensitivity interacts with fundamental pedagogical and technological aspects in modern education, such as critical thinking, the use of technology in education, and cyberbullying (Nishida

et al., 2019). Critical thinking is seen as an intrinsic component of intercultural sensitivity. Paul and Elder (2006) and Kabilan (2016) assert that the ability to think critically is essential for understanding and valuing cultural differences, facilitating a reflective and empathetic assessment of others' viewpoints (Weda et al., 2022). This mode of thinking can be enhanced by greater intercultural sensitivity, as awareness and appreciation of diverse cultural perspectives enable individuals to consider various viewpoints and challenge previous assumptions (Wu, 2015).

The use of technology in education is another relevant variable. In the digital age, technology can be a powerful tool for promoting intercultural sensitivity (Chen & Starosta, 1997), but it has also given rise to problems such as cyberbullying, a phenomenon that can hinder the development of intercultural sensitivity (Smith et al., 2008). According to the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2022), in Madrid 20% of adolescents have reported having been victims of cyberbullying, it is crucial to analyze the influence of these factors.

Objectives and Hypotheses

This work proposes three objectives: first, to analyze the relationships between the different levels of interculturality in relation to sociodemographic variables, such as age, educational level, and gender. Secondly, it is proposed to study the relationships between intercultural sensitivity, critical thinking, and the use of technology in education. Finally, we analyze whether levels of intercultural sensitivity are related with the perception of having suffered Cyberbullying.

Method

Participants

The study included a total of 835 adult participants, with 55.2% identifying as women ($n = 461$) and 44.8% as men ($n = 374$), ranging in age from 18 to 65 years ($M = 40.85$; $SD = 14.01$), all residing in Madrid, Spain. In terms of the participants' education levels, 16.6% ($n = 140$) completed primary education, 28% ($n = 233$) secondary education, 34% ($n = 283$) tertiary education, and 21.4% ($n = 179$) university education.

Instruments

An ad-hoc assessment instrument was created that included the following variables:

Intercultural Sensitivity Scale (ISS). The adapted and validated version for the Spanish context (Gómez Yepes et al., 2023) of Chen and Starosta's Intercultural Sensitivity Inventory was used (Chen & Starosta, 2000), distributed in three dimensions. The dimensions assessed were: Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment (e.g., "I think people from other cultures are narrow-minded, I don't like being with people from different cultures; I am easily annoyed when I interact with people from different cultures", "I often get discouraged when I am with people from different cultures"); Interaction Attentiveness / Interaction Engagement (I enjoy interacting with people from different cultures, I tend to wait before forming an impression of culturally different people) and Interaction confidence (I always know what to say when I interact with people from different cultures, I can be as sociable as I want when I interact with people from different cultures). The response format was Likert-type with five anchors ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree. Reliability levels for all three dimensions were adequate ($.741 < \alpha < .819$). Higher scores on each dimension imply higher levels of Intercultural Sensitivity.

Critical Thinking about Education. The scale constructed by Sosu (2013) was used, composed of 11 items that evaluate people's critical thinking in different facets in a single dimension, such as critical openness (seven items, e.g. "I usually try to think about the big picture during a discussion"), Reflective Skepticism (four items, e.g. "I usually check the credibility of the source of information before making judgments"). The reliability levels were adequate ($\alpha = .886$). The response format is 5 points (from 1 = "Strongly disagree" to 5 = "Strongly agree").

Use of Technology in Education. A short version of the Educational Technology Standards Scale (ETSS) (Naci Çoklar & Ferhan Odabaşı, 2009) was used, adapted to the local context (Etchezahar et al., 2023). The scale is made up of 10 items that investigate people's agreement with the use of technology in the educational field from different perspectives. The reliability levels were adequate ($\alpha = .927$). The response format was a Likert-type scale with 5 anchors, with 1 = Totally disagree and 5 = Totally agree.

Cyberbullying. Based on the cyberbullying dimension of the scale created by Antoniadou et al. (2016), Dimension 1 of the scale (Cyberbullying) was translated and adapted into Spanish and the Argentine context. As a result, a scale of 12 items (e.g., "Have you ever sent

photos or videos of someone to other people, without their permission, to make fun of them?”, “Have you ever said bad things about someone on the Internet to get their friends to unfollow, block, or unfriend them?”, “Have you ever sent someone a message (over the phone or the Internet) to threaten them?”) and a single dimension emerged. The two response options included were: 1. “No, never happened to me”, and 2. “Yes, it happened to me”. According to Gómez Yepes et al. (2023), it is possible to think that the participant has engaged in cyberbullying if he or she performed six or more behaviors of the 12 proposed by the evaluation (Hambleton et al., 2005).

Demographic variables. Information about age, educational level and gender was also collected.

Procedure

Data was collected through an instrument that was shared online, ensuring the participants' confidentiality. Participants were invited to take part in the study voluntarily and provided informed consent. Data was gathered via an online survey –ensuring the anonymity of the participants– through the social network Facebook, during May and June 2023. The inclusion criteria to take part in the study were to be of legal age and currently reside in the city of Madrid. Furthermore, participants were informed that the data derived from this research would be used exclusively for academic and scientific purposes, in accordance with Organic Law 3/2018, which protects personal data (Hair et al., 2010).

Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS for Windows software version 19.0 and EQS 6.1. Firstly, we have carried out a series of ANOVA's to analyze the differences between the dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity and the educational level of the participants. Next, we performed a series of *t* tests to observe differences by sex (considering Cohen's *d* to evaluate the effect size) and Pearson's correlations to study whether there were differences by age. Furthermore, we have used Chronbach's alpha to study the internal consistency of the dimensions. We also use Pearson's correlations to study the relationships with Critical Thinking, and the use of Technology in Education. Finally, a series of student *t* tests were calculated to analyze the differences between the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity and the perception of having suffered Cyberbullying.

Results

First, the differences between the three dimensions of interculturality and the educational level, gender and age of the participants were analyzed (Table 1).

Table 1. *Intercultural Sensitivity dimensions and educational level, gender, and age*

	Educational level (<i>F</i>)	Gender		<i>t</i> (Cohen's <i>d</i>)	Age
		Male (<i>M; SD</i>)	Female (<i>M; SD</i>)		
Interaction Confidence	2.905*	3.66 (.859)	3.92 (.841)	3.908*** (.305)	.123***
Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment	3.777***	1.50 (.648)	1.92 (.818)	5.595*** (.569)	.210***
Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness	1.477	3.82 (.712)	4.12 (.636)	-7.182*** (.444)	.118***

***. $p < .001$. *. $p < .05$.

Regarding the educational level, differences were observed in both “Interaction Confidence” and “Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment”. In both cases, the post hoc tests indicated the presence of two subgroups: on the one hand, the lowest means were concentrated in participants with primary and secondary education, while the highest means were in participants with tertiary and university education.

Regarding gender, statistically significant differences were observed in the three dimensions of the ISI, “Interaction confidence”, “Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness” and “Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment”; women obtained higher scores compared to men. Finally, with respect to age, significant relationships were observed with the three dimensions of intercultural sensitivity (Table 1), with low and positive strength in all dimensions.

Subsequently, the relationships between the dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity, levels of critical thinking and the use of technology in education were analyzed (Table 2).

Table 2. *Relations between the dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity, critical thinking and the use of technology in education*

	1	2	3	4	5
1. Interaction confidence	.741	.135**	.476**	.224**	.128**
2. Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment		.819	.111**	.188**	.212**
3. Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness			.807	.313**	.144**
4. Critical Thinking				.886	.207**
5. Use of Technology in Education					.927

Note. Cronbach Alfa in the diagonal.

** . $p < .01$.

As can be seen in Table 2, statistically significant relationships were presented between the levels of critical thinking and the use of technology in education with the three dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity. With respect to Critical Thinking, the strongest relationship was with the dimension “Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness”, while the weakest was with “Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment”. Regarding the use of Technology in Education, the relationships with all dimensions were low.

Finally, we analyzed whether there were differences in the three dimensions of intercultural sensitivity with respect to the perception of having suffered Cyberbullying (Table 3).

Table 3. *Intercultural Sensitivity dimensions and the perception of having suffered Cyberbullying.*

	1. No (M; SD)	2. Yes (M; SD)	<i>t</i>	Cohen’s <i>d</i>
Interaction Confidence	3.63 (.748)	3.54 (.663)	2.459*	.127
Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment	1.34 (.462)	1.44 (.451)	-3.980***	.219
Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness	3.54 (.601)	3.53 (.573)	.313	<i>n.s.</i>

*. $p < .05$.; ***. $p < .001$.

Differences were observed in the Interaction Confidence dimension with the perception of having suffered Cyberbullying, as well as with the Respect for cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment dimension. No differences were observed in the Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness dimension in any case.

Discussion

Firstly, significant differences were observed between the three dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity and the highest educational level achieved by the participants. These dimensions are "Interaction Confidence," "Respect for Cultural Differences," and "Interaction Enjoyment." Our findings align with those previously reported by Gómez Yepes et al. (2023), who emphasized that educational level is highly relevant for the development of intercultural sensitivity. Specifically, our results reveal that the dimensions "Interaction Confidence" and "Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment" are particularly linked to academic training. In both cases, higher education, such as tertiary or university studies, appears to make a considerable difference in fostering these aspects of intercultural sensitivity.

This correlation suggests that individuals with more advanced educational backgrounds are likely to develop stronger intercultural skills, possibly due to the broader perspectives and critical thinking skills acquired through higher education. Additionally, Perry and Southwell (2011) support this notion, indicating that university education can significantly enhance one's ability to engage confidently and respectfully with diverse cultures.

Therefore, our research highlights the crucial role of education in cultivating a nuanced understanding and appreciation of cultural differences, which is essential in our increasingly globalized world. As we reflect on these findings, it becomes evident that investing in higher education is not only a path to personal and professional advancement but also a vital component in fostering a more inclusive and empathetic society. By prioritizing educational opportunities that emphasize intercultural competencies, we can better prepare individuals to navigate and contribute positively to our diverse and interconnected global community.

Likewise, with respect to gender, previous studies indicated that there could be a bias towards women, who have been shown to have a greater disposition towards intercultural

empathy (Fritz et al., 2005). We also observed these results in our study, since in the three dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity women obtained higher scores compared to men (it should be noted that the dimension “Respect for Cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment” contains inverted items, which is why its results should be read backwards). Finally, with respect to demographic indicators, age is also a relevant factor, as indicated by previous studies (Duraó et al., 2023; Etchezahar et al., 2023), However, their relationship strength is low. In our results, this data is replicated.

Secondly, differences were observed in terms of the relationships of the three dimensions of Intercultural Sensitivity, critical thinking, and the use of technologies in the educational field. Regarding critical thinking, according to Paul and Elder (2006) it is considered a fundamental element for the development of intercultural sensitivity (Nishida et al., 2019). For the authors, intercultural sensitivity implies an awareness and understanding of cultural differences and similarities, as well as the ability to adapt and act appropriately in cross-cultural interactions. This is where critical thinking plays a crucial role. This skill not only enables individuals to analyze and evaluate information objectively, but also helps them to reflect on their own cultural beliefs and biases, which is essential for effective intercultural interaction.

According to Sobkowiak (2016), critical thinking is a critical skill for effectively navigating increasingly culturally diverse educational environments, especially in an expanding globalized world. In educational settings, where students come from diverse cultural backgrounds, it is even more relevant. Cultural diversity can be a source of richness, but it can also present challenges in terms of communication, teaching, and learning. A student who exhibits both critical thinking and intercultural sensitivity will be better prepared to collaborate with peers from different cultures, understand different perspectives, and contribute to an inclusive learning environment (Sobkowiak, 2016). Therefore, as expected, the results between the different dimensions of intercultural sensitivity and critical thinking were significant, with the “Interaction Engagement / Interaction Attentiveness” dimension presenting the highest relationship strength. This aspect was previously discussed by Gómez Yepes et al. (2023), who highlight that this dimension of intercultural sensitivity facilitates that knowledge and appreciation of different cultural perspectives can help individuals consider multiple points of view and question previous assumptions (Wu, 2015). Regarding the use of Technology in Education, it was a significant variable in its link with the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity,

although the strength of these relationships was low. As originally proposed by Chen and Starosta (1997), in the digital age, technology can be a powerful tool for promoting intercultural sensitivity, but this does not mean that it is a fundamental variable, unless it is analyzed from certain negative consequences that it could entail, such as the different pathologies of addiction / compulsive use (of the Internet, online games, gambling, pornography, etc.) (Weda et al., 2022).

One of the main problems resulting from the insertion of technology into our lives is cyberbullying (Albalá Genol et al., 2022), a phenomenon that can hinder the development of intercultural sensitivity (Smith et al., 2008). In our results, differences could be observed in the “Interaction Confidence” dimension, as well as with the “Respect for cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment” dimension (Pareja de Vicente et al., 2021). People with high levels of “Interaction Confidence” tend to be more empathic and, therefore, engage in fewer behaviors related to cyberbullying, given that subjects can expand their register according to the levels of openness they have and their trust (Moradi & Ghabanchi, 2019). In this sense, intercultural communication becomes intercultural behavior, which is why it is essential that these “barriers” do not arise in terms of (Zhang & Zhou, 2021). In a complementary way, the dimension “Respect for cultural Differences / Interaction Enjoyment” is directly related to the phenomenon of Bullying and is a central aspect to address, since the possibility of interaction enjoyment can only be guaranteed by respect for cultural differences, such as and as stated by Gómez Yepes et al. (2023).

Conclusion

Although the aims proposed in this work have been met, there are a series of limitations that must be considered for future studies. Firstly, the sample used was intentional. Although the number of participants was large and an attempt was made to control demographic aspects such as age and gender, the sample is not representative of the population and, therefore, the results obtained cannot be generalized. Likewise, it is also important to highlight that the relationships between the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity, critical thinking, and the use of technology in education were, in general, significant, although of low strength. This could be because there are variables that were not considered in this study that could be mediators between the dimensions of intercultural sensitivity and critical thinking, for example. Likewise, future studies could include interviews with adolescents to learn more about what

they think and how they experience these types of experiences. Finally, the way in which the participants' having suffered Bullying is also considered a limitation of the work. Although the indicator is valid and allowed us to carry out the analyzes we are looking for, it is also true that there is much more evidence to study this complex phenomenon in greater depth, which could be considered in future studies on this topic.

As could be observed from the results of this study, the levels of intercultural sensitivity are related to different variables such as educational level, gender, and age, as well as with respect to critical thinking and the use of technologies. These links are very important if we intend to advance towards better intercultural integration, combating prejudice and discrimination. This task becomes absolutely necessary given that in the context in which this study was carried out, 20% of adolescents have reported having been victims of cyberbullying (INE, 2023), and this number continues to grow year by year.

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